

Biochemical Study of Hypothyroidism Subjects and Relationship to Overweight

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Abstract

This article evaluates the relationship between thyroid hormone levels, including TSH, fT4, T4, T3, and lipid profiles, such as total cholesterol, LDL, and HDL, in obese individuals compared to healthy ones. The research included 80 individuals, of which 40 were categorized as obese (20 males and 20 females) and 40 were healthy controls (also 20 males and 20 females). All participants were between the ages of 25 and 45. To perform thyroid gland tests, blood samples of 10 ml were taken from both healthy and subjects participants without EDTA and put into test tubes. The plain tube containing blood was centrifuged to separate the serum for further thyroid function and chemical tests. The ELISA device was used following the manufacturer's instructions. The study found significant differences in the levels of TSH hormone between subjects and healthy participants based on the collected data. Furthermore, subjects had significantly lower levels of fT4 hormone in subjects (4.4 ± 2.0) compared to healthy controls (8.1 ± 2.1). The research findings indicated a significant reduction in T4 hormone levels (4.3 ± 1.3) in subjects, which was consistent in both males and females and corresponded with the increase in TSH hormone levels (9.17 ± 2.0) observed in subjects individuals compared to healthy subjects (2.98 ± 2.1). However, there were no significant alterations in T3 hormone levels among subjects when compared to healthy individuals. Hence, the study concludes that there is a definitive correlation between hypothyroidism and obesity.

Introduction

One of the greatest health hazards of our time is obesity [1]. As per [2], obesity has become increasingly prevalent across the globe since the mid-1970s. Obesity can lead to various health issues such as diabetes, dyslipidemia, renal disease, cardiovascular disease, cancer, and all-cause mortality. Therefore, excessive obesity can significantly contribute to early mortality among middle-aged individuals. Additionally, thyroid dysfunction is one of the many endocrine disorders linked to obesity, particularly central obesity. According to [3,4], the fact that T3 regulates energy metabolism, and thermogenesis, and plays a crucial role in regulating food intake, lipid and glucose metabolism, and the oxidation of fatty acids explains why it is not surprising that TSH levels are higher in obesity. However, it is difficult to identify obese individuals who are experiencing a shortage of thyroid hormones despite having elevated TSH levels. Therefore, it is recommended to evaluate the plasma levels of thyroid hormones before suspecting hypothyroidism in obese individuals with elevated TSH values.

According to [5] it has been confirmed that the World Health Organization (WHO) considers excessive adiposity as the defining characteristic of obesity, which is a complicated multifactorial non-communicable disease that can have negative impacts on a person's health. Moreover, obesity is a major contributor to the development of several non-communicable diseases (NCDs), such as sleep apnea, osteoarthritis, gout, dyslipidemia, type 2 diabetes, coronary heart disease, hypertension, and stroke. Obesity is also the most significant modifiable risk factor for type 2 diabetes. It is projected that by 2025, approximately one in every five adults around the world will be obese. Moreover, [6] add that both subclinical and overt hyperthyroidism has been associated with an elevated Basal Metabolic Index (BMI) and a higher incidence of obesity. Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in regulating energy balance, lipid and glucose metabolism, and hypertension. Obesity is a chronic disease that affects people of all ages and is prevalent in almost every country, irrespective of physical activity levels. This

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non-communicable disorder is characterized by low-grade inflammation and is associated with alterations in body weight and composition, body temperature, as well as total and resting energy expenditure.

Moreover, [7] noted that an imbalance between energy consumption and expenditure leads to obesity. Moreover, [7] add that a lack of physical activity and a decrease in basal metabolic rate reduce energy expenditure. According to [8], weight gain occurs due to an underactive thyroid gland that reduces the release rate of hormones, leading to an imbalance in metabolic processes. This imbalance causes fat to accumulate in unwanted areas of the body, including the belly and buttocks.

[9] add that to tackle the problem, one should undergo medical examinations to determine the suitable medical intervention. This may involve taking thyroxin pills to make up for the hormone deficiency, following specific dietary plans, engaging in various physical activities, ensuring sufficient fluid intake, particularly water, and getting enough rest and sleep during the treatment period. The impact of thyroid hormone on crucial physiological functions in humans includes improving glucose metabolism, stimulating fat and protein metabolism, increasing basal metabolic rate (BMR), influencing the cardiovascular system, and stimulating the central nervous system [7]. The objective of the present article is to investigate the correlation between obesity and hypothyroidism.

Material and Methods

The article aimed to compare individuals who were healthy with those who were obese. The study includes 80 involved. The study design was case-control study. The study technique was simple random sample (40 males and 40 females equally distributed among the two groups). The healthy control group included 20 males and 20 females, while the other group consisted of 20 male and 20 female subjects. The samples were collected with the assistance of medical personnel from a laboratory situated in the AL-Karama Teaching Hospital located in the Waist Province of Iraq. The inclusion both groups shared similar characteristics, including the absence of any history of thyroid or other endocrine disorders, chronic illnesses such as heart disease, diabetes, or hypertension, and not taking any medications that may impact thyroid function, such as levothyroxine or antithyroid medications and exclusion the patients under the 24 age. A specialist physician conducted medical examinations to confirm the eligibility of men and women who provided the sample (between October 15, 2021, and March 15, 2022). Additionally, a control group consisting of 40 healthy individuals aged 25 to 45 years, comprising both men and women, was chosen.

Their normal hormonal condition was verified through laboratory testing. Spectral studies and biochemical

analyses were conducted on samples collected from both subjects and healthy individuals to examine the thyroid gland. The most accurate laboratory assessment for thyroid function was found to be the serum TSH test, which is recommended for detecting primary hypothyroidism. In cases where the serum TSH level is found to be elevated, a serum-free thyroxin (T4) level evaluation should be performed as a follow-up test. The study technique was sample random.

Accordingly, the classification of the participants as obese was determined by their body mass index (BMI) using the development curves for each gender and the WHO cut-off criteria [6]. The weight of the subjects was measured using a digital scale, while their BMI was calculated by dividing their weight in kilograms by the square of their height in meters (kg/m). To obtain blood samples, a 10 ml vein was collected from individuals showing signs of hypothyroidism.

Blood was taken from both healthy and sick participants without using Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid (EDTA). The blood samples were then centrifuged to separate the serum for conducting thyroid function tests and chemical analyses. The ELISA device was used as per the manufacturer's guidelines. All participants provided informed consent for their participation in the study. The study utilized hypotheses testing (specifically a test about means) to compare the two groups, with an independent sample t-test serving as the statistical method of data analysis. The SPSS APM 26 program was employed to perform the statistical analysis, focusing on analyzing quantitative variables. The results showed significant differences between the means of the two groups, except for T3. The researchers utilized the Student T-test to determine any differences between the control healthy group and the subjects.

Results

Table (1) below demonstrates a significant difference in the levels of TSH hormone between subjects and healthy individuals. The average TSH hormone value in the study's participants was (2.98 ± 2.1) , which was consistent for most age groups. In contrast, subject participants had an average TSH hormone value of (9.17 ± 2.0) which was high in subjects than that in the control.

This test is crucial in evaluating the gland's efficiency and is considered one of the fundamental examinations required by physicians. Accordingly, knowing the thyroid's inactivity or activity, analytical T4 and FT4 are crucial.

Findings revealed a significant decrease in fT4 hormone levels (4.4 ± 2.0) in subjects compared to healthy individuals (8.1 ± 2.1) .

Additionally, the data indicated a considerable decline in T4 hormone levels in subjects (4.3 ± 1.3) of both sexes,

coinciding with an increase in TSH hormone levels, as compared to healthy subject (9.1±2.1).

Thus, there were no significant differences in T3 hormone levels between subject (0.38±0.3) and healthy individuals (0.37±0.1), according to the results. However, a noteworthy association between obesity and hypothyroidism was observed, with subjects exhibiting significantly higher levels of Total cholesterol and LDL compared to healthy subjects (233.1±6.1), (188.8±2.0); (60.3±3.1), (33.8±2.3) respectively.

Finally, individuals with hypothyroidism had higher levels of HDL-cholesterol at (65.8±3.1) compared to healthy individuals at (36.7±4.1). Additionally, a significant increase in fat levels was observed in hypothyroid subjects (95.4±3.4 kg) compared to healthy subjects (70.5±3.0 kg). This increase in fat levels is associated with weight gain as fat accumulates in the body.

Table 1: Demographic, Anthropometric and Other Characteristics of Obese the Subjects

Parameter	Control women and men Age (25-45) n=40	Subjects' women and men Age (25-45) n=40	P- value
TSH (µIU/mL)	2.98±2.1	9.17±2.0 S	P≤0.01
fT4 (pg/mL)	8.1±2.1	4.4±2.0 S	P≤0.01
T4 (pg/mL)	9.1±2.1	4.3±1.3 S	P≤0.01
T3 (pg/mL)	0.37±0.1	0.38±0.3 Ns	-
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	188.8± 2.0	233.1± 6.1 S	P≤0.01
LDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)	33.8±2.3	60.3± 3.1 S	P≤0.01
HDL-cholesterol (mg/dL)	36.7± 4.1	65.8± 3.1 S	P≤0.01
Weight (kg)	70 .5±3.0	95. 4±3.4 S	P≤0.01

Note: refers to the parameter that is important to control.

Discussion

The incidence of hypothyroidism is increasing across all age groups. The thyroid gland produces hormones that are essential for metabolic processes that facilitate calorie burning. Neglecting the disease can lead to various complications.

A study revealed a significant difference in thyroid hormone levels between subjects and healthy individuals, with an increase in the TSH hormone. Hashimoto's disease can cause the thyroid gland to produce insufficient hormones, leading to hypothyroidism.

This autoimmune condition is characterized by inflammation of the thyroid and the presence of thyroid-inhibiting globin antibodies in the blood serum. It is more common in middle-aged women and can result in symptoms such as fatigue and weight gain.

These antibodies can bind to the hormone receptor TSH. TSH (thyroid-stimulating hormone) is the most important and delicate test used for both diagnosing and monitoring hypothyroidism. Essentially,

TSH measures the level of satisfaction that the body has with the amount of hormone produced by the thyroid. In the case of an excessively high TSH level, it may indicate the presence of hypothyroidism [10].

As stated by [11] the hormones FT4 and T4 underwent significant changes, which can be attributed to the interaction between pituitary cells and the thyroid. The pituitary gland releases TSH into the bloodstream, which stimulates the thyroid. When T4 levels are optimal, it may be due to a reduction in protein

production that responds to thyroid hormones. The pituitary gland secretes adequate TSH to maintain the same level of T4 production. Conversely, a decrease in T4 levels triggers the pituitary gland to secrete more TSH, prompting the thyroid to generate more T4. High TSH levels correspond to low T4 levels. If T4 levels are too high, the pituitary gland produces less TSH, instructing the thyroid to generate less T4.

Accordingly, obese individuals' T3 levels are either normal or increased. However, T3 levels in obese people are comparable to those in healthy individuals. Furthermore, obese individuals exhibit a significant increase in cholesterol levels that cannot be attributed to increased cholesterol production or decreased bile acid synthesis.

Hypothyroidism is likely a contributing factor to weight gain in affected subjects. Obesity appears to develop and persist in affected individuals [12].

The hypercholesterolemia in obese subjects with hypothyroidism may be partly due to their condition, as per reference [13].

However, research on obese individuals has shown that thyroid hormone can increase cholesterol production regardless of body weight, as per reference [15].

Treating hypothyroid subjects with thyroid hormone has been found to significantly reduce their blood lipid values, as per reference [16].

Comparing the lipid levels of hypothyroid subjects to a control group showed a significant difference, with hypothyroid individuals having considerably higher levels of cholesterol, LDL, and HDL.

Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in lipid metabolism, with a deficiency leading to hyperlipidemia, a known risk factor for atherosclerotic disease, as per reference [16].

In cases of overt hypothyroidism, there is a reduction in the liver's LDL receptors, leading to a rise in both total HDL and LDL levels. Additionally, studies have demonstrated heightened triglyceride levels among subjects with overt hypothyroidism.

Hypothyroidism results in a reduced ability to remove endogenous and exogenous triglycerides from the bloodstream, leading to this effect.

Comparing hypothyroid subjects with a control group revealed that their HDL levels were elevated. The decreased functioning of the thyroid gland is responsible for the higher HDL levels observed in hypothyroid subjects [17].

From another aspect, numerous studies have been carried out to investigate the relationships among thyroid hormones.

Obesity is a complex health issue influenced by both genetic and environmental factors, characterized by an excess of energy intake relative to expenditure. Obesity has become a significant public health challenge, with its prevalence escalating rapidly over the past three decades [11].

In addition, the rise in obesity rates has been accompanied by a corresponding increase in the prevalence of hypertension, insulin resistance (IR), and metabolic syndrome (MS). The functioning of thyroid hormones plays a role in the metabolism of fat and glucose, and high levels of TSH could be merely a consequence of obesity. It is crucial to be pragmatic and not attribute all weight gain to hypothyroidism.

The amount of authentic weight gain caused by hypothyroidism and the extent of weight loss after reaching a euthyroid state through treatment remain inadequately studied. Contrary to popular belief, treating overt hypothyroidism produces very little weight reduction [18,19].

Conclusion

The available data obtained from the study carried out in the Wasit Province of Iraq have substantiated the existence of a substantial association between the prevalence of hypothyroidism and obesity.

The study findings support the notion that obesity can be considered a risk factor for hypothyroidism, and the higher the body mass index (BMI), the greater the likelihood of developing hypothyroidism.

This study's results are of considerable importance, as both obesity and hypothyroidism have become widespread health problems in the region, and understanding the relationship between the two could potentially help develop more effective prevention and management strategies. The findings could also provide insight into the underlying mechanisms and

pathways that link obesity to hypothyroidism, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between these two health issues.

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Disclaimer

None

Conflict of Interest

None

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None

References

- [1] Dev N, Sankar J, Vinay MV. Functions of Thyroid Hormones. In: Imam, S., Ahmad, S. (eds) *Thyroid Disorders*. Springer, Cham; 2016. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-25871-3_2
- [2] Lass N, Barth A, Reinehr T. Thyroid Volume and Thyroid Function Parameters Are Independently Associated with Weight Status in Overweight Children. *Horm Res Paediatr*. 2020;93(5):279-286. doi: 10.1159/000509786
- [3] García-Solís P, García OP, Hernández-Puga G, Sánchez-Tusie AA, Sáenz-Luna CE, Hernández-Montiel HL, Solís-S JC. Thyroid hormones and obesity: a known but poorly understood relationship. *Endokrynol Pol*. 2018;69(3):292-303. doi: 10.5603/EP.2018.0032
- [4] Zeleke M, Badanie A, Asefa ET, Reta Demissie W, Chala G, Aman H, Feyisa TO, Habte ML. Assessment of Electrocardiographic Changes and Associated Factors Among Thyroid Dysfunction Patients Attending Jimma Medical Center, Southwest Ethiopia: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Int J Gen Med*. 2023 May 26;16:2035-2046. doi: 10.2147/IJGM.S407513
- [5] Brent GA, Weetman AP. Hypothyroidism and thyroiditis. In: *Williams textbook of endocrinology 2016* Jan 1 (pp. 416-448). Elsevier; 2016.
- [6] Sweeney LB. Hypothyroidism: an update. *South African Family Practice* 2012;54(5):384-90. doi: 10.1080/20786204.2012.10874256
- [7] Sanyal D, Raychaudhuri M. Hypothyroidism and obesity: An intriguing link. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab*. 2016 Jul-Aug;20(4):554-7. doi: 10.4103/2230-8210.183454
- [8] Özer S, Bütün İ, Sönmezgöz E, Yılmaz R, Demir O. Relationships Among Thyroid Hormones And Obesity Severity, Metabolic Syndrome And Its Components In

Turkish Children With Obesity. *Nutr Hosp.* 2015 Aug 1;32(2):645-51. doi: 10.3305/nh.2015.32.2.9212

[9] Walczak K, Sieminska L. Obesity and Thyroid Axis. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021 Sep 7;18(18):9434. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18189434

[10] Tng EL. The debate on treating subclinical hypothyroidism. *Singapore Med J.* 2016 Oct;57(10):539-545. doi: 10.11622/smedj.2016165

[11] Ma S, Jing F, Xu C, Zhou L, Song Y, Yu C, Jiang D, Gao L, Li Y, Guan Q, Zhao J. Thyrotropin and obesity: increased adipose triglyceride content through glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase 3. *Sci Rep.* 2015 Jan 6;5:7633. doi: 10.1038/srep07633

[12] Abu-Khudir R, Larrivéé-Vanier S, Wasserman JD, Deladoëy J. Disorders of thyroid morphogenesis. *Best Pract Res Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2017 Mar;31(2):143-159. doi: 10.1016/j.beem.2017.04.008

[13] Nettore IC, Cacace V, De Fusco C, Colao A, Macchia PE. The molecular causes of thyroid dysgenesis: a systematic review. *J Endocrinol Invest.* 2013 Sep;36(8):654-64. doi: 10.3275/8973

[14] Szinnai G. Genetics of normal and abnormal thyroid development in humans. *Best Pract Res Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2014 Mar;28(2):133-50. doi: 10.1016/j.beem.2013.08.005

[15] Witkowska-Sędek E, Kucharska A, Rumińska M, Pyrżak B. Thyroid dysfunction in obese and overweight children. *Endokrynol Pol.* 2017;68(1):54-60. doi: 10.5603/EP.2017.0007

[16] Milionis A, Milionis C. Correlation between body mass index and thyroid function in euthyroid individuals in Greece. *International Scholarly Research Notices.* 2013;2013.

[17] Sinha RA, Singh BK, Yen PM. Direct effects of thyroid hormones on hepatic lipid metabolism. *Nat Rev Endocrinol.* 2018 May;14(5):259-269. doi: 10.1038/nrendo.2018.10

[18] Liu J, Sun W, Dong W, Wang Z, Zhang P, Zhang T, Zhang H. Risk factors for post-thyroidectomy haemorrhage: a meta-analysis. *Eur J Endocrinol.* 2017 May;176(5):591-602. doi: 10.1530/EJE-16-0757

[19] Thomason SK. *Sampling.* third edition. 2012; p59-60.

